

Vision of sustainable trade regimes

MATS Deliverable 5.1

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Funded by
the European Union

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Summary

WP5 started in M21 (March 2023), according to the work plan schedule in the Description of Action in the GA. WP5 builds on results of WP1-4 and WP6. The aim of the WP is to jointly develop a MATS vision of a more sustainable, resilient food system that builds on equitable economic partnerships in agricultural trade as well as transition pathways towards this vision, which will be described in deliverable 5.2. The visioning process focuses on a joint vision for the whole MATS consortium within the context of alternative trade regimes. The visioning workshop was held during MATS project meeting in Tanzania. In preparation of the workshop: (1) Mini-Workshop in the context of the MATS project meeting on May 15th & 16th, 2023 was organized with background information on the visioning process and first ideas on the vision elements based on different case studies. (2) Individual meetings with case study representatives took place. This assisted in identifying the most important aspects for the vision. With this background four webinars were organized in preparation of the workshop on transition pathways in March. The whole process of task 5.1 will be summarized in the policy brief on the visioning, which is as well part of deliverable 5.1.

Deliverable title: Vision of sustainable trade regimes

Deliverable number: 5.1

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Visioning Workshop for Transition Pathways

Background

The goal of the visioning workshop was to facilitate collaborative envisioning of successful management and adaptation to upcoming changes across various dimensions such as environmental, social sustainability, market and investment, trade policy, and government. The workshop aimed at the formulation of vision statements that are shared by all case studies within the MATS project as well as develop initial ideas for implementable option for action (transition pathways).

Approach

The workshop took place in Moshi, Tanzania on October 24th and 25th, 2023. The workshop was conducted in the context of the MATS Annual Meeting, with the concept and facilitation provided by Fraunhofer ISI. The target group included MATS Case Studies Representatives, external workshop participants, and further project partners.

On the first day of the workshop, participants were welcomed and introduced to the visioning and workshop approach. The agenda and the background of the workshop were presented, and participants were given an opportunity to introduce themselves. The first work step involved dividing the case study related people into their most interested dimensions of sustainability and dividing the rest of the group equally into the four dimensions of sustainability.

During the working phase, participants prioritized and expanded vision statement written on cards and identified potentials and challenges for implementation of the vision. Conflicts were identified and resolved if necessary. The work continued in new group constellations using the World Cafe-Approach. In the plenary session, hosts presented short summaries of the discussed topics per dimension, and all participants voted on the most important points for a MATS vision to be taken into the next round. There were four hosts supporting the discussions at the tables from the following partners: ESRF, UPM, OWW, NWU.

On the second day, the workshop started with a summary of the results from the previous day and an introduction to the workshop approach for day two. Group formations were done, and participants worked on templates on option actions with independently chosen coffee breaks. Numbered templates were processed, and clustered on the wall around the vision statements. The workshop concluded with a personal review, final roundtable, and wrap-up session where participants discussed the greatest potentials and challenges on the way to a common vision.

The workshop ended with an outlook on the next steps. The collected ideas and outcomes from the workshop will contribute to the development of transition pathways and policy recommendations for sustainable trade relations in agricultural value chains as part of the MATS project.

Developing Transition Pathways - The Webinar Series

Background

The "Developing Transition Pathways - The Webinar Series" was organized to prepare for a workshop on transition pathways and policy recommendations in Brussels in March. The series consisted of four webinars, each focusing on one dimension of sustainability. The goal was to gather input and perspectives from a wide range of stakeholders, including experts from case studies, trade, and agriculture.

The invitation sent to case study representatives emphasized the importance of their involvement in sharing the invitation with their respective stakeholders. The webinars aimed to integrate "the view from outside" the MATS project, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives.

Approach and tools

Each webinar followed a consistent agenda. It began with a dial-in and technical check to ensure smooth participation. The session then commenced with a warm welcome and introduction, setting the stage for the discussions that followed.

The presentation of the Miro board and workshop approach was a crucial part of each webinar. The Miro board served as a collaborative platform, allowing participants to visualize and contribute to the development of transition pathways. The agenda encouraged participants to generate new actions, provide suggestions, and engage in discussions to improve and adapt existing approaches.

Following the active participation and contribution phase, time was allocated for reflection. Participants had the opportunity to absorb the discussions, review the actions collected, and draw connections between different ideas and perspectives.

Next steps in the project were discussed at the end of each webinar, providing updates on the progress made and outlining the future direction. The webinars

concluded with a formal end-of-event message, expressing gratitude to the participants for their valuable contributions.

Throughout the webinars, the Teams platform facilitated seamless online collaboration, while the Miro board served as a visual aid and interactive workspace for participants to collectively begin to shape the transition pathways.

Results

During the webinars, participants actively shared their ideas and suggestions on the measures that could be taken to achieve the shared vision. To organize and categorize these ideas, a timeline approach was adopted. The participants' ideas were divided into three categories: short-term measures (up to 3 years), medium-term measures (3 to 7 years), and long-term measures (7 to 10 years).

The resulting roadmap was structured based on the thematic elements of the vision. The thematic elements served as the foundation for organizing and prioritizing the measures identified by the participants. By aligning the roadmap with the vision's themes, it ensured that the proposed measures were coherent and contributed to the overall objectives.

The timeline categorization provided a clear sense of the urgency and timeframes associated with each measure. Short-term measures aimed at addressing immediate actions within a relatively short period, while medium-term measures focused on more comprehensive initiatives that could be implemented within a few years. Long-term measures were designed to tackle complex challenges and required a more extended timeframe for implementation.

Figures 1 to 4 show the main part of the Miro board for each of the four dimensions with the three categories of time on the top and the vision statement on the right hand side.

FIGURE 2: MIRO BOARD FROM THE WEBINAR ON THE SOCIAL AND HUMAN DIMENSION

FIGURE 4: MIRO BOARD FROM THE WEBINAR ON THE DIMENSION OF ECONOMY AND MARKETS

Follow-up

The outcomes from the webinars, including the categorized measures and the structured sketch of the roadmap, formed the basis for further discussions, refinement, and implementation planning in subsequent workshops and project activities.

By combining the thematic elements of the vision-parts - according to the different sustainability dimensions - with the categorized timeline, the resulting integrated roadmap will provide a strategic framework for the development of transition pathways. It highlighted the necessary measures and actions to be taken at different stages, ensuring a systematic and coherent approach towards achieving the shared vision. This roadmap will be further developed during the WP6 workshop on "Transition Pathways" in Brussels in March 2024.

Policy brief: The MATS Vision –Visioning process on desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments

Introduction

To meet the overall goal of deriving transition pathways for desirable changes in agricultural trade relations towards greater sustainability and to formulate corresponding policy recommendations, it is necessary to define where we as a group aim to go. The MATS visioning assists to define this direction and describes desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments with a focus on equitable economic partnerships in sustainable agricultural trade for the time horizon 2035+.

In broad terms, we want to work towards a more sustainable and resilient food system with economic and trade partnerships where partners recognize each other as “equals” (Juncker, 2018). To find transition pathways towards this desired state, this definition had to be deconstructed into more concrete vision statements with the help of the 15 MATS case studies contributing their on-the-ground/evidence-based insights.

Highlights

The visioning process is a participatory approach including stakeholders directly involved in the MATS consortium. These stakeholders will continue to play a pivotal role in developing transition pathways. Additional stakeholders and external experts from industry, research, policy as well as civil society will be invited to join the discussion and expand the knowledge base.

The visioning process was initiated by reviewing the 15 MATS case studies’ mid-term reports. Vision statements were derived and collected along the four previously defined sustainability dimensions – “policy, governance and regulation”; “social and human dimensions”; “natural capital”, and “economy and markets”. In addition, online consultations with the different case studies were held to get preliminary information on the collected statements. With this foundation, the MATS case studies and core team members - especially those engaged with institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks and with

civil-society actors, stakeholders and policymakers - came together in Moshi/Tanzania to discuss the findings in a moderated participatory workshop setting. This approach ensured that relevant issues were considered and discussed. The results of this process were again reflected in a series of webinars, open to the MATS case studies, core team as well as external participants from industry, research or civil society.

FIGURE 5: OVERVIEW OF THE STEPS OF THE VISIONING PROCESS

During the visioning workshop the inner circle of stakeholders discussed a desired future state of sustainable agricultural trade in 2035+. It became apparent that despite their differences, the case studies have many areas of overlap in their common objectives for sustainable agricultural trade.

During the visioning workshop, the development of transition pathways for more sustainable agricultural trade was also started by collecting initial ideas for action aimed at realizing the desired vision. These will help to derive policy recommendations as the project evolves.

Discussion points/Policy suggestions

The case study reports and individual discussions with the case studies **provided a differentiated picture of a desired future**. Among the vision statements considered and discussed included the following: (a) "All workers

on cocoa farms earn at least a living wage”, which is regarded as closely aligned to a regional context in nature and can be applied to several country contexts; (b) “Alignment of EU agricultural, trade, investment, and development policies for sustainable value chains”, which is considered holistic in nature but can also be transferable to different regions; (c) “strong local institutions and capacities for sustainable trade” whose actions were already brought to the discussion in the visioning workshop”; and, (d) “established bodies provide some capacity building initiatives to processors and exporters for meeting WTO rules, regulations, and EU requirements”, where several actions were added during the four online sessions, covering the whole time range from short, middle to long term.

It noteworthy that since agricultural trade is interwoven in the agri-food system and constitutes only one step in the value chain, **a considerable part of the vision statements addressed the state of agricultural production.**

The visioning process on desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments revealed, among others, that old and new policies are needed, that sustainable water management practices in agriculture touches all four dimensions of sustainability, and that decentralization and less bureaucracy may be critical factors in guaranteeing smallholder farmers access to markets and fair prices.

Appendix

In the following, the slides from the presentation of the webinar series will be provided.

Developing Transition Pathways The Webinar Series

WP5:Co-designing transition pathways and policy recommendations

5.-8. February 2024

Ariane, Ewa, Anna | Fraunhofer ISI

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

Fraunhofer

ISI

AGENDA

February 8 | 12:00-13:30

11:45 Dial-in and technical check

12:00 Welcome and Introduction

12:15 Presentation of the Miro board and approach

**12:20 Collect new actions, adapt, improve, suggest, discuss,
draw connections**

01:10 Reflection

01:20 Next Steps

01:30 End of the event

MATS project

- MATS is a 3.5 year duration project
- The consortium comprises **14 partners**
- **15 case studies** from different regions, various value chains
- MATS aims to identify **key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy**
- MATS want to foster the **positive** and reduce the **negative impacts** of trade on sustainable development and human rights
- MATS develops new tools for a **systemic analysis** of the interactions between **agricultural trade, investments, sustainability and development**

MATS case studies

- <https://sustainable-agri-trade.eu/case-studies-overview/>

CASE STUDIES ▾

Overview

[Interactive
Dashboard](#)

MATS case studies

STH Interactive Dashboard

Continent

Alle ▼

Country

Alle ▼

Topic

Alle ▼

Focus

Alle ▼

Commodity

Alle ▼

Methodology

Alle ▼

SDG

Alle ▼

Filters

15
Case Studies

Transition Pathways Sustainable Trade

The overall **GOAL** is to derive transition pathways for **desirable changes in trade relations** towards **greater sustainability** and to formulate corresponding **policy recommendations**.

Visioning process on desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments

October 23-27,
2023 Moshi,
Tanzania

Include the view from outside: collect more input on concrete actions to reach the vision statements and draw connections

February 05-08,
2024, online

Elaborate concrete transition pathways for desirable changes

March 6, 2024,
Brussels

Vision[ing] in MATS

- The 2035+ vision provides an **ambitious but principally feasible, positive and differentiated picture** of the state of sustainable trade.
- Underlying **MATS vision** from the MATS proposal:
 - a **more sustainable and resilient** food system with economic and trade partnerships where **partners recognize each other as “equals”** (MATS proposal)
 - MATS aims to identify key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy that **foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of trade on sustainable development and human rights** (MATS Homepage)
- **Deep Dive in the Case Studies:** Statements about the desirable future of the agricultural trade from the **individual case studies** were collected.
- The MATS vision was developed along the **4 dimensions of sustainability**

Number	Topic	Key aspects	Main focus
1.	Reducing poverty among smallholder farmers through enhanced trade regimes and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania	Improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers through trade value chains; localisation of food systems, strengthening of territorial markets	Uganda, Tanzania
2.	Intra-EU trade, resilience and social sustainability; the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics	Resilience of trade-dependent food value chains in the context of intra-EU agri-food trade and social sustainability; sustainability and equity	Finland, Sweden, EU
3.	Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production	Mapping the linkages of dairy production and dairy trade with environmental externalities and production of ecosystem services	Finland, EU, trade partners
4.	Priority Intervention Requirements to Enhance the Capacity of Sub-Saharan African (SSA) Countries to Improve the Volume and Quality of Agri-food Exports - The cases of Tanzania, Ethiopia, Uganda, and Ghana	Standards and market access; challenges related to WTO Rules and Regulations and/or EU requirements; strengthening of territorial markets	Sub-Saharan Africa
5.	Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana	Emerging markets; poultry chains; role of policy regulation regarding animal welfare, inputs and trade; competitiveness, sustainability, livelihoods	Ghana
6.	Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers	Experiences, obstacles, impact and lessons learned from a multistakeholder initiative on sustainability standards in the cocoa sector	EU, Côte d'Ivoire
7.	Impacts of EU policies on local dairy value chains in West Africa	EU agricultural, trade, investment and development policies; impact on the development of local, fair and sustainable dairy chains	EU, Africa
8.	Belgian imports of ethanol from sugar cane: shared responsibilities among EU MS of human rights violations	EU biofuel policies and mandates; sustainability criteria biofuels; EU climate funding; carbon markets, offset mechanism; palm oil; land use change	EU, America, Africa, Asia
9.	Human rights due diligence in the coffee value chain	Integrating human rights and environmental due diligence in coffee chains; impact on production practices and smallholder farmers	EU, Uganda
10.	Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development	EU agricultural, trade, investment and development policies; impact on local, fair, sustainable beef chains, including consumers and retailers	EU, Africa, South America
11.	Private standards and sustainable trade	Impact of processors/retailers' standards on development of local, fair, sustainable food chains; GLOBAL G.A.P.	Africa, Asia
12.	Ethical trade initiatives in the South African wine industry	Assessment of local and global ethical trade programmes in South Africa (e.g. Fair Trade, Ethical Trading Initiative, Ethical Trade Association)	South Africa, trade partners
13.	Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets	Labour costs; additional costs resulting from environmental regulation; total production costs; processing and retail	EU, Africa, America
14.	Governing trade to influence land-use and food systems pathways: The expansion of soybeans-meat complexes in the MATOPIBA Brazilian frontier	How different trade agreements, institutions, rules and established practices could shape the expansion of the soybeans-meat complex in the MATOPIBA region to ensure more sustainable, equitable, inclusive, and resilient outcomes	EU, Brazil
15.	Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreements (DCFTAs) between the EU and selected North African countries, and their impact on agriculture, access to water and sustainability	Impact of EU-Tunisia FTA on incomes and market opportunities for farmers, fishers, breeders; ecological resilience, especially water scarcity	EU, N Africa (Tunisia)

Four dimensions of sustainability in MATS

- sub categories: social dimension, human dimension, economy and markets, natural capital, and policy, governance & regulations
- Each Case Study covers different dimensions and thematic areas of sustainability.

Social and human dimension

Natural capital

Economy and markets

Policy, governance and regulations

	SDG #	MULTI-COUNTRY TRADE FOCUS				NATIONAL PRODUCTION FOCUS							PRODUCTION OUTCOMES FOCUS				#
		CS4	CS10	CS14	CS15	CS1	CS2	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS3	CS5	CS9	
Social dimension																	
Ownership rights	5.a.1			X				X		X	X	X					5
Social Protection	1.3.1							X	X	X	X						5
Discrimination	10.3.1	X						X							X		4
Unemployment rates	8.5.2	X			X			X				X				X	6
Human rights (Child labour, forced labour)	8.7.1	X															1
Working conditions	8.3.1		X	X	X			X	X	X			X			X	8
	8.8.2		X	X				X	X	X		X	X				8
Human dimension																	
Poverty rates	1.1.1		X	X	X			X	X	X	X		X		X	X	11
Access to basic services	1.4.1	X							X	X							3
Food security and nutrition (e.g., famine, nutrition, food quality)	2.1.1							X		X				X			4
	2.1.2				X			X						X			3
	2.2.2							X						X			2
Health	3.9.1									X							1
	3.9.2	X								X							2
	3.8.1																0
Economy and Markets																	
Volume traded	17.11.1	X	X	X	X			X			X	X					9
Prices (unit value, distortions...)	2.c.1								X					X			2
Income creation	8.5.1							X						X			2
Subsidies & tariff lines	2.3.2		X		X			X	X		X		X	X			10
	12.c.1									X							1
	10.a.1																0
Production	2.3.1	X		X				X		X		X	X			X	9
	2.4.1	X		X				X	X					X		X	5
Value added (GDP)	12.3.1							X	X				X	X			4
	8.1.1				X												1
	8.2.1																0
Natural capital																	
Exposure to extreme climatic events	13.1.1	X															1
Access to environment-friendly technology	17.7.1							X		X						X	3
Natural resource use	6.4.1																0
	6.4.2	X		X									X				3
	7.2.1																0
	8.4.1		X	X	X			X				X	X				6
GHG emissions	13.2.2		X	X						X			X				4
Water-related ecosystems	6.6.1			X													1
Landscape changes	11.3.1			X				X		X							3
Water pollution	15.1.1	X								X							2
	3.9.2	X															1
	6.3.2	X															1
Soil erosion	15.3.1							X									1
Policy, governance & regulations																	
Legal Framework	5.1.1	X			X			X	X	X	X	X					7
	2.a.1		X					X	X				X		X	X	6
Public revenues and expenditure (agriculture sector, essential services, pro-poor, and conservation/ biodiversity)	2.a.2	X	X					X	X			X	X	X			7
	2.b.1	X	X		X			X	X			X	X				7
	1.a.2				X			X		X							4
	1.b.1								X	X							2
	15.a.1							X				X					2

Figure: Visual representation of the key focus areas of the case studies considered in the MATS project (D2.4)

Four dimensions of sustainability in MATS

- sub categories: social dimension, human dimension, economy and markets, natural capital, and policy, governance & regulations
- Each Case Study covers different dimensions and thematic areas of sustainability.

	SDG #	MULTI-COUNTRY TRADE FOCUS				NATIONAL PRODUCTION FOCUS							PRODUCTION OUTCOMES FOCUS				#
		CS4	CS10	CS14	CS15	CS1	CS2	CS6	CS7	CS8	CS11	CS12	CS13	CS3	CS5	CS9	
Social and human dimension																	
Social dimension																	
Ownership rights	5.a.1			X				X		X	X	X					
Social Protection	1.3.1							X	X	X	X	X					
Discrimination	10.3.1	X						X						X			
Unemployment rates	8.5.2	X				X		X				X				X	
Human rights (Child labour, forced labour)	8.7.1	X				X		X								X	
Working conditions	8.3.1		X	X	X		X	X	X			X			X		
	8.8.2		X	X			X	X	X		X	X				X	
Human dimension																	
Poverty rates	1.1.1		X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X		X	X		
Access to basic services	1.4.1	X							X	X							
Food security and nutrition (e.g., famine, nutrition, food quality)	2.1.1					X		X	X					X			
	2.1.2				X	X								X			
	2.2.2					X								X			
Health	3.9.1								X								
	3.9.2	X							X								
	3.8.1																
Economy and Markets																	
Volume traded	17.11.1	X	X	X	X	X			X		X	X	X				
Prices (unit value, distortions...)	2.c.1							X						X			
Income creation	8.5.1						X							X			
Subsidies & tariff lines	2.3.2		X		X	X		X	X		X		X	X			
	12.c.1								X								
	10.a.1																
Production	2.3.1	X		X			X		X		X	X	X		X		
	2.4.1	X		X			X	X						X			
Value added (GDP)	12.3.1					X	X						X	X			
	8.1.1				X												
	8.2.1																
Natural capital																	
Exposure to extreme climatic events	13.1.1	X															
Access to environment-friendly technology	17.7.1						X		X						X		
Natural resource use	6.4.1																
	6.4.2	X		X										X			
	7.2.1																
	8.4.1			X	X	X		X				X	X				
GHG emissions	13.2.2		X	X					X				X				
Water-related ecosystems	6.6.1			X													
Landscape changes	11.3.1			X													
Water pollution	15.1.1	X						X		X							
	3.9.2	X															
	6.3.2	X															
Soil erosion	15.3.1							X									
Policy, governance & regulations																	
Legal Framework	5.1.1	X			X			X	X	X	X	X					
	2.a.1		X			X	X					X		X	X		
Public revenues and expenditure (agriculture sector, essential services, pro-poor, and conservation/ biodiversity)	2.a.2	X	X			X	X					X		X			
	2.b.1	X	X		X	X	X					X					
	1.a.2				X		X		X	X							
	1.b.1							X	X								
	15.a.1	X										X					

Figure: Visual representation of the key focus areas of the case studies considered in the MATS project (D2.4)

Webinar series

Collect new actions, adapt, improve, suggest, discuss, draw connections towards the vision statements...

Let's go to the Miroboard

Onboarding

Miro basics and warm-up

Miro Basics

NAVIGATING THE MIRO BOARD

METHOD 1 You can change the background color of the board. Click on the color palette in the top right corner to select a new color. The background color will change immediately.

METHOD 2 You can change the background color of the board. Click on the color palette in the top right corner to select a new color. The background color will change immediately.

METHOD 3 You can change the background color of the board. Click on the color palette in the top right corner to select a new color. The background color will change immediately.

Annotations: A red arrow points from the text "Intra Video - English" to a red YouTube icon on the board. A yellow arrow points from the text "New in Miro?" to the top right corner of the board.

Welcome to our MATS Webinar Series

Technical Warm-up and Introduction

AGENDA

11:45 Dial-in and technical check

12:00 Welcome and Introduction

12:10 Presentation of the Miro board and approach

12:20 Collect new actions, adapt, improve, suggest, discuss, draw connections

01:10 Reflection

01:20 Next Steps

01:30 End of the event

Technical Support
Ewa.Doenitz@isi.fraunhofer.de

Back to M5Team:
https://teams.microsoft.com/Meeting?join=0%3Bmeeting_QG6301M00QMT8M00M0QYLWE+MjkiLDRkZGkNjcsMDN0840?brand=2701&context=9f7b92714fb72679822010300c492846123e03e4d880a17149422924%2D2208f922%3a%22b4958be-4413-4172be84-c6e-0218029b220821

Next steps in overview

Integration of the options for action form all 4 dimensions.

Social and human dimension

Natural capital

Economy and markets

Policy, governance and regulations

- Are there any synergy effects?
- Are there any mismatches regarding the timeline?

Thank you!

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Acknowledging the EU funding

- Grant Agreement: "Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:
 - (a) display the EU emblem and
 - (b) include the following text:
 - "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000751"
- When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

